

PREPSOIL DELIVERABLE

Title	Conclusion Report on Training Needs for Monitoring and Assessment of Soil Health with Curriculum for Pilot Course
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Deliverable description:	<p>This deliverable, produced under Task 5.4 of the PREPSOIL project, summarises the identification of training needs and the development of a pilot course to support soil health monitoring in line with the Soil Monitoring Law and the EU Mission Soil. It includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An analysis of training needs based on a survey targeting competent authorities across the EU. • The design and implementation of a four-session online pilot training held in June 2025. • An evaluation of the training’s relevance and effectiveness based on participant feedback. <p>The report provides a first step towards future capacity-building initiatives and serves as a reference for scaling up soil monitoring training at EU level.</p>
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1. Context and background

PREPSOIL Task 5.4 on Capacity building for improved monitoring knowledge base is framed within the European ambition to achieve healthy soils by 2050, as outlined in the EU Soil Strategy for 2030. This strategy, adopted in 2021, is a cornerstone of the European Green Deal and proposes actions for the protection, restoration, and sustainable use of soils, including the establishment of 100 Living Labs (LL) and Light Houses (LH). The Soil Strategy is also aligned with other key Green Deal initiatives such as the Zero Pollution Action Plan, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and the Farm to Fork Strategy, reinforcing an integrated approach.

In this context, the European Commission (EC) proposed in July 2023 a Soil Monitoring Law (SML) to establish a common framework for assessing soil health across the EU. The legislative process progressed during 2024, with the European Parliament adopting its position in April and the Council reaching a general approach in June. A provisional political agreement on the final text was reached in April 2025. Although the directive will formally enter into force after the conclusion of PREPSOIL, its agreed content has already served as a guide for Member States to begin developing the necessary capacities.

The future SML does not impose direct obligations on farmers or foresters, but rather assigns responsibility to public authorities. Each Member State will be required to have qualified technical and administrative personnel capable of designing national soil monitoring networks, applying harmonised methodologies, and reporting results with accuracy and comparability across the EU. Public bodies will also be obliged to provide independent advice, targeted training, and continuous support to land managers. This underscores the importance of capacity building: countries must ensure that their institutions possess the necessary skills, structures, and resources to fulfil these new responsibilities. Capacity building is not merely a complementary tool; it is the foundation for coherent, efficient, and fair implementation. Without a common language on soil, consistent criteria, and training adapted to all levels, including laboratory technicians, agricultural advisors, and environmental managers, there is a risk of fragmented efforts, duplication of resources, and compromised policy effectiveness.

In addition, the SML introduces a key institutional innovation: the designation of soil districts, at least at the NUTS1 level, which represents an opportunity to bring soil governance closer to the ground in a more territorial and operational manner. This structure reinforces the need for both vertical and horizontal coordination, as well as institutional capacities that enable the implementation of multi-level governance.

Ultimately, the success of the European vision for healthy soils depends on having the right people, structures, and competences to bring it into practice. This is precisely the objective of PREPSOIL Task 5.4, developed under the framework of the EU Mission “A Soil Deal for Europe” and aimed at strengthening the knowledge base for soil monitoring.

1.1. Initial vision and planning

The original vision for Task 5.4 was outlined in the project's Grant Agreement (GA), approved in 2022. According to this document, the objective was “to initiate the training of actors responsible for monitoring soil health.” To this end, several specific goals were defined:

1. Identify training needs related to soil health monitoring and its indicators.
2. Build on the results of previous WP5 tasks to design the training program.
3. Exchange and discuss with national hubs, projects and other stakeholders.
4. Develop a training curriculum and prepare four pilot workshops/knowledge sharing sessions
5. Include content on indicators, harmonised protocols, threshold values, and data interpretation.
6. Publish all training materials through the PREPSOIL integrative platform (one-stop shop).

These elements provided a solid starting point and clear expected outputs (e.g., needs assessment reports, training materials), setting the initial course for the task.

1.2. Implementation and strategic adjustments

When implementation began in 2024, “**Phase 2**”, the team realised that it would be necessary to adjust the original approach of the task. The main reason was the evolving regulatory context: the proposal for the SML, presented in 2023, had not yet been formally adopted in 2024, and its final approval was not expected until after the conclusion of PREPSOIL. This posed a key challenge: strictly following the plan outlined in the GA could result in training that was too closely tied to legislation not yet in force.

Therefore, during an internal coordination meeting held in the first half of 2024, a strategic decision was made to adjust the training program from its original design in order to ensure its immediate relevance and usefulness, even before the new legal framework becomes operational. Specifically, the team chose to base the training on well-established scientific and technical content, while leaving room to incorporate regulatory updates at a later stage, once the law became a reality.

This shift in approach led to the adoption of a stepwise or “layered learning” pedagogy. The training begins by reinforcing fundamental scientific knowledge on soils and indicators, and then gradually incorporates legal and policy elements as they are defined. This model offers a dual advantage: on the one hand, it ensures that the training is immediately applicable in the current context (for instance, aligned with the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) or existing biodiversity strategies); on the other hand, it allows for easy updates with the specific provisions of the new directive once approved.

In summary, during 2024 Task 5.4 was reoriented from its initial design. The original plan envisioned training tailored to a specific future legal framework, whereas the revised program focuses on delivering a more agile and immediately useful training, grounded in solid foundations and adaptable to legislative developments. Then, the program will take a knowledge-sharing approach rather than a standard training course. This proactive decision helped to navigate regulatory uncertainty and ensured that the capacity-building efforts would benefit countries even before the SML entered into force, laying the groundwork for its future transposition.

2. Identification of training needs and priorities

In parallel with these strategic adjustments, the team launched activities to thoroughly identify training needs related to soil monitoring. Beginning in May 2024, the task entered “**Phase 2**”, explicitly focused on the needs expected to arise with the future SML. A training needs assessment report was prepared, focused on the key challenges that the directive would pose once in force (Annex 3.2). This report was based on a legal and technical analysis and a series of technical meetings with experts from the EC (DG AGRI and DG ENV). These high-level exchanges allowed the team to anticipate which knowledge and skills would be essential for implementing the new regulation across Member States.

A key criterion was to distinguish needs according to the different user profiles who will be involved in implementing the soil monitoring system. The report therefore structured training priorities with three main target groups in mind: policymakers, technical staff, and data managers. From this consultation and analysis process, a consolidated list of priority training topics emerged, including:

- The legal and policy framework of the directive.
- Soil health indicators and associated monitoring parameters.
- Data interpretation (how to analyse and draw conclusions from monitoring data).
- Use of digital tools for soil monitoring.
- Design of national monitoring programs aligned with the European scheme.

These areas highlighted where training efforts should be focused to facilitate the smooth and consistent transposition and implementation of the law across the EU. It is important to note that from the outset, the identification of training needs combined both quantitative and qualitative methods.

On the one hand, surveys were planned to gather broad input from target groups. On the other hand, specific workshops and dialogues were organised with key stakeholders. In addition to exchanges with the EC, discussions were also held with representatives of the Soil Health National Hubs and other relevant national institutions. As a result of these interactions, the PREPSOIL consortium (with INIA-CSIC leading this task) produced an internal working document listing possible training topics required for implementing the SML, aligned with the articles of the proposed directive (Annex 3.1). This preliminary list covered subjects ranging from legal transposition and public participation to soil sampling, remote sensing tools, and contaminated land management. For each thematic block, specific training content was proposed and expert feedback was requested. For instance, in the legal field, proposed modules included content on the directive’s legal details and its links with other environmental legislation, national transposition procedures, and Member State obligations (e.g. soil districts and competent authorities).

On this point, EC experts highlighted the need to assess “whether certain legal topics are truly necessary” for Member States, suggesting that the curriculum should be adjusted based on a rigorous needs analysis. In turn, the PREPSOIL team refined the proposals, for example, by emphasising the inclusion of harmonised sampling and analysis methods, and the latest European advances in soil

biodiversity indicators, given the rapid developments in this technical area. These back-and-forth exchanges reflect an iterative process of consolidating needs, combining expert input from the EC with internal reflections from WP5 to ensure relevance and up-to-date content.

As part of this analytical phase, an online consultation was launched in early 2025 to expand the evidence base. This survey, titled *“Training needs assessment for soil health management and the implementation of the Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive”*, targeted a broad range of stakeholders: national and regional policymakers, implementation technicians, Commission officials, scientists, and more. Its objective was to identify priority-training needs in two areas:

- General soil health management (monitoring techniques, key indicators, decision-making).
- The transposition and implementation of the Soil Monitoring Directive into national frameworks.

The survey introduction explained that the collected information would be used to design “tailored” training programs enabling stakeholders to address the challenges of soil monitoring and related policy implementation. It also highlighted the role of PREPSOIL Task 5.4 in building capacity at the European level and stated that results would be tested through pilot training sessions with experts.

Through a set of questions, participants assessed the relevance of various training topics (e.g. deepening knowledge on indicators like bulk density, soil organic carbon, microbial biodiversity; training in sampling methods; adapting indicators to different land uses; designing representative monitoring plans, etc.) using a scale from “not important” to “very important”. Respondents could also provide qualitative comments. The responses to this survey, together with the findings from the needs assessment report, helped prioritise the most demanded topics and competencies, providing a solid evidence base for the design of the training program.

3. Co-creation and validation of the curriculum

Once the core training needs had been identified and consolidated, Task 5.4 moved into “**Phase 3**” (August to December 2024), focused on co-creating and validating the training content with stakeholders. Rather than developing the curriculum in isolation, the PREPSOIL team opted for a participatory process that engaged a wide range of European actors involved in soil health. During this phase, multiple meetings and consultations were held with different stakeholder groups, enriching the training program with diverse perspectives and ensuring its alignment with real-world practices and expectations in the sector.

Exchanges were established with 22 European projects under the Mission Soil, including initiatives such as AI4SoilHealth, HuMUS, NB SOIL, CREDIBLE, MRV4SOC, and LILAS4SOIL, among others. These projects, also working on various aspects of soil monitoring and improvement, brought valuable technical knowledge and synergies to the process. Coordination meetings were also held with representatives of the EC (DG AGRI, DG ENV), focusing on aligning the training with the forthcoming EU regulatory framework and the needs of national administrations. In parallel, exchanges and bilateral meeting were conducted with several key national institutions, particularly from Spain

(coordinating country for the task), including the National Institute for Agricultural and Food Research and Technology (INIA-CSIC) soil experts, the CSIC's SoilBIO Platform experts, and ministries such as the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA) and the Ministry for the Ecological Transition (MITECO). These national bodies contributed on-the-ground perspectives on how the training could be implemented in each country, ensuring that the program would be practical and applicable at the institutional level.

The co-creation process helped refine the proposed content and delivery formats through ongoing feedback from participants. The discussions not only validated the previously identified needs but also revealed real-world challenges that the training should address, such as current difficulties in soil sampling, the interpretation of certain indicators, and administrative barriers. Participants also offered pedagogical suggestions on how to better deliver specific topics, for instance by combining theory and practice, using case studies, or fostering cross-country exchange to maximise learning effectiveness. All these inputs were recorded and analysed by the T5.4 team. The initially proposed content was significantly enriched thanks to contributions from the expert community and end users, confirming the value of the chosen methodological approach.

In parallel, the PREPSOIL consortium conducted an internal validation process. For example, during the coordination meeting held on 14 January 2025, the partners jointly reviewed progress on Task 5.4, revisited the strategic shift agreed upon months earlier, and defined the next key steps. At that meeting, the target groups for the training were reaffirmed: public staff in charge of soil data management under a unified reporting system; policymakers who must take decisions based on soil data; and members of Living Labs involved in co-creation processes. The partners also confirmed the activities planned to complete the task, including the dissemination of the ongoing survey, curriculum development with expert input, implementation of pilot workshops, evaluation of the pilots, and final consolidation of the training program. This multi-actor validation process, both external and internal, provided solid confidence that the training program was responding to real needs, was technically robust, and aligned with emerging EU policies.

4. Development of the training program

After incorporating all the recommendations, the team proceeded to design of the training program. This stage corresponded to “**Phase 4**” of the task, during which the tentative content and modular structure of the curriculum were defined. The result was a program structured around four main thematic modules, designed to comprehensively address the different dimensions identified in previous phases.

Module 1 - Scientific foundations and regulatory framework:

This module provides the conceptual basis regarding the importance of soil, its ecosystem functions, and the global challenges associated with soil degradation. It also offers an overview of the evolving policy and regulatory landscape, including the European perspective such as the SML, the Mission Soil, the EU Soil Strategy for 2030, the Farm to Fork Strategy, the EUBiodiversity

Strategy for 2030 and their interconnections, as well as relevant international initiatives such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals, FAO actions, and IPCC reports. This module also introduces the key soil health indicators and the harmonised framework proposed under the SML, setting the stage for the following modules.

Module 2 - Soil health indicators and their complexity:

This module goes into the definition, measurement and interpretation of various physical, chemical and biological indicators. It addresses the technical challenges and limitations associated with each indicator, such as bulk density, organic carbon content, pH and microbial biodiversity, as well as the issue of variability and uncertainty when applying standardised threshold values across diverse contexts. The objective is to ensure that participants understand the complexity inherent in assessing soil health and the need for flexible approaches depending on land use type, whether agricultural, forestry, or urban, and local conditions.

Module 3 - Monitoring methods and digital tools:

This module covers practical methodologies for soil observation, including sampling techniques, field protocols, and laboratory analysis. It also addresses advanced technologies that are transforming soil monitoring, particularly digital soil mapping and the application of remote sensing technologies such as satellite data and sensor networks to estimate soil health indicators at various scales. The module explores the use of digital platforms and geographic information systems for managing and analysing geo-referenced data, as well as tools for collecting participatory data through citizen science and how to integrate these with official monitoring systems. All content is aligned with European best practices, ensuring data protection and quality.

Module 4 - Interpretation of results and application to public policy:

This final module trains participants to translate soil monitoring data into useful knowledge for decision-making. It includes techniques for evaluating collected information, preparing clear and accessible reports, and using performance indicators to detect long-term trends. It focuses on how to interpret soil health indicators against reference values or thresholds, identify trends, and draw conclusions on the status and resilience of soils. The module also explores how to integrate these results into policy design and implementation, for example by assessing the impact of CAP interventions on soil carbon or identifying priority areas for action. Moreover, it includes a discussion of public participation and transparency mechanisms related to soil information, in line with the principles of the directive, such as the right to environmental information and the involvement of landowners and citizens in decision-making. The overall goal is to provide participants the skills needed to turn technical data into effective management and policy strategies.

The curriculum was developed progressively and in an integrated way, as planned after the initial adjustments. Content from Tasks 5.1 and 5.2 of PREPSOIL was incorporated, including newly proposed indicators for different soil types and the feasibility of using satellite observation for key indicators.

National case studies provided by project partners were also integrated, showcasing monitoring experiences across countries, as well as examples from relevant European projects whose findings complemented the training content. Thanks to the integration of multiple sources, the final program achieved a balance between technical soundness and policy relevance, while remaining flexible enough to be adapted to different national contexts. One of the guiding principles was to allow modular adjustments according to the particularities of each country or region, while maintaining a coherent methodological approach.

As for the teaching methodology and delivery formats, a dynamic approach was adopted in line with the suggestions received during the co-creation phase. The program combines theoretical training with practical activities, including expert lectures, facilitated discussions, applied exercises and real case studies. For example, participants will work with soil data from pilot projects and simulate decision-making processes based on those data to reinforce practical skills. Opportunities for peer-to-peer exchange, including networking and discussion forums, were also envisaged in order to foster a community of practice around soil monitoring. All formats were validated with project partners to ensure they are appropriate and feasible for the target audience. Furthermore, it was confirmed that all training materials, presentations, guides, recordings and more, will be published on the PREPSOIL website as an open repository, in line with the aim of creating a one-stop-shop for accessing the knowledge generated. In this way, the benefits of the training will extend beyond the participants in the workshops, reaching a wider audience across Europe.

5. Structure and implementation of the pilot phase

With the training plan clearly defined, Task 5.4 entered “**Phase 5**”, focused on implementing the pilot programme and verifying its effectiveness. The team identified three core objectives for this final phase: to deliver high-quality technical training, to facilitate knowledge exchange, and to promote the dissemination of good practices among participants. To achieve these aims, implementation was structured around four pilot workshops, grouped into two main sessions (Annex 1). Each session brought together complementary thematic areas. The workshops were conceived as **knowledge-sharing sessions**, including **practical cases and examples**, with a targeted and participatory approach that encouraged audience interaction through comments, Q&A exchanges, and feedback on the suitability and quality of the content and its delivery.

The speakers for the pilot sessions were selected through a combination of three criteria. First, experts were chosen based on their involvement in EU Mission Soil projects whose results were most relevant to the training needs identified during Phase 4. These experts had worked on content that directly addressed the gaps and priorities highlighted in the training needs assessment. Second, project partners from Tasks 5.1 and 5.2 of PREPSOIL were invited to contribute their findings and ensure consistency across the work package. Finally, a number of trusted external experts were selected, particularly those with proven experience in soil health and monitoring and who had been collaborating with INIA-CSIC in related initiatives. This approach ensured a balanced and high-quality set of lectures, combining scientific soundness, policy relevance, and practical applicability.

All training materials developed for the sessions, including the video recordings of the pilot workshops, the lectures delivered, and additional informative resources (including Annex 3.1 and Annex 3.2), are publicly available on the PREPSOIL website.

Session 1: Innovating soil monitoring. From indicators to policy impact

Workshop 1:

Lecture 1: Key indicators and their complexity

Speakers: Agnieszka Klimkowicz-Pawlas and Grzegorz Siebielec (IUNG, Poland)

Content: Description of physical, chemical, and biological indicators and their inclusion in the upcoming Soil Monitoring Law. Emphasis on the need for flexible approaches based on land use and regional context.

Lecture 2: Monitoring soil health under the future European Directive

Speaker: Claire Chenu (INRAE and EJP SOIL, France)

Content: Lessons learned from EJP SOIL on harmonization, tiered biological indicator systems, and open data practices.

Workshop 2:

Lecture 1: Monitoring indicators and the Soil Quality Index (SQI)

Speaker: Adolfo Perdomo (University of La Laguna, Spain)

Content: Description of 40 indicators, weighting methods, and the application of the SQI in Lanzarote.

Lecture 2: Building the conceptual framework for the agro ecological transition

Speaker: José Manuel Ávila (Agro ecology Partnership and LifeWatch ERIC)

Content: Design of specific monitoring plans to assess agroecological progress.

Session 2: Digital tools for soil health monitoring

Workshop 3:

Lecture 1: Assessing the impact of CAP measures on soil carbon

Speaker: José Luis Gabriel (INIA-CSIC, Spain)

Content: National validation of agricultural practices that increase soil organic carbon. Preliminary results and expected outcomes for carbon sequestration.

Lecture 2: Remote sensing applied to soil monitoring

Speaker: Pierre Renault (INRAE, France)

Content: Use of remote sensors and digital soil mapping to generate maps of soil properties and associated uncertainties.

Workshop 4:

Lecture 1: Decision support tools for carbon MRV (MRV4SOC)

Speakers: Marta Gómez (GMV, Spain) and Bertrand Guenet (CNRS, France)

Content: Hybrid systems combining in situ data, remote sensing, and process-based models for Tier 3 verification schemes.

Lecture 2: Soil monitoring strategies in southern Europe

Speaker: Mercedes Román (NEIKER, Spain)

Content: Sampling and digital mapping methods adapted to Mediterranean and agricultural contexts, with implications for soil health and food security.

These pilot workshops were designed as a testing ground to assess the quality and relevance of the training program prior to its final consolidation. Altogether, the pilot sessions addressed seven key topics, combining expert presentations, interactive discussions, and practical exercises. Two training days were scheduled, one for each session, on 13 June 2025 and 20 June 2025 respectively. The participants included technical staff from various countries, EC representatives, and other stakeholders, ensuring a diverse and pan-European audience.

Structured feedback was collected from participants during the workshops through evaluation forms and final group discussions. The goal was to assess the achievement of learning objectives and identify potential areas for improvement. Specifically, the evaluation focused on whether the content was clear, useful, and applicable, and whether the methodology, including the balance between theory and practice and the technical level, was appropriate for the target audience.

Following the workshops, the Task 5.4 team analysed the evaluations and identified lessons learned. According to the established plan, these findings would serve to fine-tune the final curriculum. For example, any topic that was not sufficiently understood could be reinforced in the final materials, and any unmet needs could be addressed through the inclusion of additional modules. The modular design of the training program made it possible to introduce targeted changes without altering the overall structure.

The expected outcome is a consolidated training package, ready to be scaled up through additional workshop editions, national training sessions, and other delivery formats. This final version is also to be submitted to the EC as one of the deliverables of the project. All training materials developed, including presentations, manuals, practical cases, and recordings of the pilot sessions, will be published on the PREPSOIL online platform, creating an accessible knowledge base for Member States and the broader soil community.

In this way, Task 5.4 provides a lasting legacy in the form of a complete, tested, and policy-aligned training program, ready to support countries in the establishment of their national soil monitoring systems under the future European legal framework.

5.1. Overview of the pilot Session 1 lectures contents

Session 1.1. Innovating Soil Monitoring: From Indicators to Policy Impact (13 June 2025)

Lecture 1. Key indicators and their complexity.

Presenters: *Agnieszka Klimkowicz-Pawlas & Grzegorz Siebielec*

Objective: To elucidate the scientific and technical foundations of key soil health indicators, highlighting the complexities and challenges associated with their application—particularly within the framework of the EU Soil Monitoring Law (SML).

Scope of the Presentation:

- Classification and relevance of physical, chemical, and biological indicators.
- Thresholds, target values, and regional adaptability.
- Overview of indicators included in the Soil Monitoring Law (SML).
- Emphasis on the need for context-specific and flexible monitoring approaches.

1. Soil Indicators – General Classification (per Bünemann et al. 2018):

- **Physical** (e.g. bulk density, porosity)
- **Chemical** (e.g. soil organic carbon, salinity)
- **Biological** (e.g. microbial biomass, enzyme activity)

2. Key Physical Indicators:

- **Bulk Density (BD):** Influences root penetration, porosity, water holding capacity, and microbial activity. Optimal values vary by soil texture.
- **Water Retention & Infiltration:** Governed by soil texture and structure; includes AWC, WHC, Ksat, and air capacity.

3. Key Chemical Indicators:

- **Soil Organic Carbon (SOC):** Integral to soil fertility and structure; categorized into fast, intermediate, and slow pools based on turnover.
- **Soil Salinity:** Evaluated via electrical conductivity (EC); excess salts impair plant water uptake and microbial function.

4. Key Biological Indicators:

- **Functional Indicators:** Enzyme activity (e.g., β -glucosidase, urease), microbial respiration, and biomass.
- **Structural Indicators:** Diversity and abundance of soil biota (bacteria, fungi, nematodes, etc.).

- **Soil Biodiversity:** Assessed through techniques like DNA metabarcoding, PFLA, and QBS-ar.

5. Indicator Selection & Thresholds:

- Selection criteria: sensitivity, specificity, measurability, reliability.
- Types of values:
 - **Target values:** Desired optimal conditions.
 - **Critical thresholds:** Point of intervention.
 - **Trigger values:** Early warning signals.

6. Indicators under the Soil Monitoring Law (SML):

Organized in four parts:

- **Part A:** Salinization, SOC loss, subsoil compaction (EU-level criteria).
- **Part B:** Erosion, excess nutrients, contamination, infiltration (MS-level criteria).
- **Part C:** Topsoil compaction, acidification, biodiversity loss (descriptive, no thresholds).
- **Part D:** Soil sealing and destruction.

7. Specific Indicators and Their Complexity:

- **Salinization:** EC thresholds; classification into saline, sodic, alkaline.
- **SOC Loss:** Evaluated by SOC content, SOC/clay ratio, and SOC stock over time.
- **Compaction:** Bulk density benchmarks by soil texture; optional indicators include K_{sat} and air capacity.
- **Erosion:** Soil loss rates; critical thresholds range from 2 to $>10 \text{ t ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.
- **Excess Nutrients:** Phosphorus and nitrogen concentrations; SOC:N ratios; N:P ratios.
- **Contamination:** Heavy metals (e.g., Cd, Pb, Hg), organic pollutants (e.g., PFAS, pesticides).
- **Water Retention:** Measured via WHC, K_{sat} , AWC; sensitive to land use and climate.
- **Acidification:** pH and base saturation; base cation: Al ratios for forest soils.
- **Soil Biodiversity Loss:** No universal thresholds; interpretation often relative to baseline or prior conditions.
- **Sealing & Destruction:** Quantified via % sealed surface; assessed with Earth observation data.

8. Contextual Adaptation of Indicators: Indicators must reflect:

- Soil type (mineral vs organic)
- Land use (agriculture, forest, urban, post-industrial)
- Regional climate and geography
- Specific monitoring objectives (risk, stock, policy assessment)

9. Supporting Frameworks and Initiatives:

- **Soil Monitoring Law (2024):** Legal basis for standardized monitoring across the EU.
- **Mission Soil / NBSOIL Project:** Aims to enhance indicator usability through digital tools and capacity building.

- **Soil Academy:** Offers training on advanced soil monitoring and advisory tools.

Discussion Points:

- Relevance and applicability of specific indicators in national/regional contexts.
- Availability and adequacy of threshold values.
- Implementation challenges for the SML-recommended indicators.

Lecture 2. Monitoring Soil Health in the framework of the future EU Soil Directive. Lessons learned and recommendations from EJP SOIL.

Presenters: *Claire Chenu*

Objective: To share lessons learned and formulate recommendations from the EJP SOIL project regarding soil health monitoring in the context of the upcoming **Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive (SMD)**.

1. Review of Current National Soil Monitoring Systems

- **19 EU Member States** currently operate soil monitoring systems.
- National systems differ in **sampling depth, layout, and methodologies** (Bispo et al. 2021).
- Key comparison with **LUCAS Soil** shows:
 - Uneven **spatial distribution**.
 - Gaps in **land cover and soil type representativity**.
 - Significant differences in **SOC, pH, and clay content**.

Recommendation: Improve cooperation and integration between LUCAS and national systems through:

- Shared scoring functions,
- Transfer functions,
- Validation via double sampling (e.g. Belgian Presidency exercise).

2. Soil Indicators: Review and Alignment

Comparison between EJP SOIL and SMD indicators (Deliverable 6.5):

Parameter	Agreement	Suggested changes
SOC	SOC content & stock	Replace SOC/clay with SOC/SOCexp or SOCmax
Nutrients	Total N, Extractable P	Add P stocks, C/N ratio
CEC	Not in SMD	Recommend adding CEC, ESP
Biodiversity	Included	Specify functional & structural indicators
Soil structure	Bulk density	Confirmed
Water	AWC	Recommend adding infiltration and porosity

Contamination	Trace elements, organics	Confirmed
Soil erosion	Soil loss rate	Confirmed

3. Biological Indicators – Tiered Approach

Tier I Indicators (functional and structural):

Type	Indicator	Standard	Characteristics
Functional	Microbial biomass C	ISO 14240	Sensitive, cheap
Functional	Microbial respiration	ISO 16072	Sensitive to SOC, pollution, sealing
Functional	Enzyme activity	ISO 20130, TS 22939	Sensitive to degradation
Structural	Earthworms, Mesofauna, Nematodes	ISO 23611 series	Easy, functional/structural
Structural	Microbiota (bacteria/fungi)	Metabarcoding	Costs decreasing

Key Insight:

- Functional indicators assess **biological activity and nutrient cycling**, not biodiversity.
- Structural indicators assess **biodiversity**, not functional performance.

4. Setting Targets and Thresholds

Methodological approaches:

- **Fixed values** (e.g. regulatory limits),
- **Reference-based** ("natural" or undisturbed states),
- **Statistical distribution** (e.g. percentiles),
- **Relative change** (based on baseline monitoring data).

Examples:

- Denmark: SOC threshold at 60%, target at 80% for grassland.
- Italy: SOC threshold 12.5%, target 87.5%.

5. Additional Recommendations for SMD Implementation

- Harmonise **sampling periodicity**: 5 years is a practical compromise.
- Include **topsoil and subsoil** layers.
- Define **appropriate sampling periods** (e.g. spring/autumn for biodiversity).
- **Avoid sampling post-management intervention** (e.g. after tillage or pesticide application).
- Estimated costs per site: **€1,000–2,500**.

6. Data Management and Sharing

- Central role for EJP SOIL in supporting **metadata harmonization** and **open access**:
 - **660 datasets** catalogued (national, EJP SOIL, ESDAC).

- Integration with **EUSO** and **SoilWise** platforms.
- Tools and standards:
 - **Geopackage_INSPIRE_SOIL** for data exchange,
 - Vocabularies (GLOSIS),
 - Wikis and code lists for data providers.

7. Conceptual Clarification: Soil Health vs. Soil Quality

- **Soil Health**: current state and capacity to deliver ecosystem services sustainably.
- **Soil Quality**: potential capability considering context (soil type, land use).
- Distinction based on sustainability (People, Planet, Profit – P, P, P) and actual functionality.

Take-Home Messages

- Harmonised monitoring is essential.
- Sampling strategy determines representativity and comparability.
- A **tiered system for biological indicators** is practical and effective.
- Realistic and adaptable **targets and thresholds** are key to policy relevance.
- **Open data** infrastructure is a prerequisite for science-based policy and long-term monitoring.

Session 1.2. - Innovating Soil Monitoring: From Indicators to Policy Impact – 13 June 2025

Lecture 3. Soil Monitoring Indicators and the SQI: A Practical Approach

Presenter: *Adolfo Perdomo González*

Objective: To present a structured approach to **soil monitoring**, covering:

- Key **physical, chemical, and biochemical** indicators.
- A methodology for their **integration via a Soil Quality Index (SQI)**.
- A **case study** application in a degraded arid environment (Lanzarote, Canary Islands).

1. Soil Monitoring Indicators – Scope and Classification

Definition:

Soil indicators are **quantifiable, repeatable variables** used to assess:

- Soil degradation,
- Restoration effectiveness,
- Land management outcomes.

Classification:

- **Physical**: bulk density, aggregate stability, water retention properties, texture.
- **Chemical**: EC, pH, macro- and micronutrients (N, P, K, B, Fe, etc.), soluble ions, CaCO₃.

- **Biochemical:** microbial biomass carbon, respiration, enzymatic activities (β -glucosidase, urease, phosphatase), qCO_2 .

2. Key Indicator Descriptions

Physical Indicators:

- **Bulk Density:** Reflects porosity and compaction. Critical for root growth and infiltration.
- **Aggregate Stability:** Proxy for erosion resistance and structure.
- **Available Water (AWC):** Difference between field capacity and permanent wilting point.
- **Texture Ratio:** (Sand + Silt)/Clay; provides insight into physical behavior of soils.

Chemical Indicators:

- **EC:** Reflects salinity risk.
- **pH:** Influences nutrient availability and microbial activity.
- **SAR & ESP:** Related to sodicity; high values degrade soil structure.
- **Nutrient Levels:** Total N, Olsen P, exchangeable K, etc.
- **SOC & SLOC:** Carbon pools essential for fertility and structure; labile C is more sensitive to land use.

Biochemical Indicators:

- **Microbial Biomass C:** Indicates biological fertility.
- **Soil Respiration:** Measures microbial activity.
- **Enzymes:** β -glucosidase (C cycling), urease (N cycling), phosphatase (P cycling).

3. Soil Quality Index (SQI)

Purpose: To synthesize diverse soil variables into a **single index (0–1 scale)** reflecting overall soil quality.

Methodological Steps:

1. **Outlier treatment** and data cleaning.
2. **Scoring transformation:**
 - More-is-better (e.g. SOC, enzyme activity),
 - Less-is-better (e.g. BD, EC),
 - Optimum (e.g. pH, texture ratio).
3. **Variable selection:**
 - PPS > 0.5 removed (redundancy),
 - ANOVA to test significance,
 - PCA to retain key factors (eigenvalue > 1; >5% variance).
4. **Weighting via PCA:**
 - Each indicator weighted by its variance contribution.
5. **Final SQI:** Weighted sum of individual scores.

4. Case Study: Arid Ecosystem in Lanzarote (Canary Islands)

Study Area:

- Altos de Famara (~600 m elevation), a degraded arid zone.
- Climate: ~110 mm precipitation/year, strong winds, high solar radiation.

Assessment Findings:

- Severe **biological degradation**: low microbial activity and species richness (bacteria, fungi, coleoptera).
- **Physical degradation**: erosion, structural breakdown, poor infiltration.
- **Chemical degradation**: very low SOC and nutrient levels.

Ecological Zoning:

Soils classified by vegetation type (native vs. exotic) and degradation level.

Take-Home Messages:

- The SQI enables **objective, integrative assessment** of soil health across variables.
- Indicator scoring must be **context-sensitive**, not universally prescriptive.
- The **biochemical dimension** (particularly microbial and enzymatic activity) is **highly sensitive to degradation and restoration efforts**.
- This methodology is practical, reproducible, and particularly useful in **monitoring degraded or restored sites**.

Lecture 4. Building the conceptual framework for monitoring agroecological transition

Presenter: José Manuel Ávila

Objective: To present the conceptual and operational frameworks under development in **Work Package 5 (WP5)** of the European **Agroecology Partnership**, aiming to **monitor the agroecological transition**, with a strong emphasis on **soil health** and sustainability performance across scales.

1. Context: The Agroecology Partnership

- **Horizon Europe** co-funded initiative (2024–2033).
- 72 partners across 26 countries.
- Strategic goal: to “team up and unlock the transition to agroecology” by 2050.
- Budget: **€300 million**, including up to 7 **transnational calls for research**.

2. Objectives of WP5: Data & Monitoring

Led by **LifeWatch ERIC (ES)** with co-lead **MINLNV (NL)** and multiple European partners.

WP5 aims to:

- **Develop conceptual frameworks and indicators** to track agroecological transitions.
- Support **impact assessment** across social, environmental, economic and governance dimensions.
- Create a robust **data infrastructure** to ensure interoperability, accessibility and long-term monitoring.
- Enable **evidence-based policy making**.

3. Monitoring Framework Architecture

The framework is composed of two main components:

A. Conceptual Framework (CF):

Based on **Theory of Change**, integrates:

1. **Transition Dynamics:** How interventions influence change over time.
2. **Agroecological Integration:** Degree of implementation of **13 HLPE agroecology principles**.
3. **Sustainability Impact Assessment:** Multidimensional evaluation (environmental, social, economic, governance).

B. Monitoring Operationalisation Framework (MOpF):

Adapted from Lamanna et al. (2023), this layer operationalizes:

- **Monitoring settings** (spatial scale, actors, purpose),
- Collaboration protocols,
- Indicators mapping and feedback loops.

4. Key Achievements to Date

- **Data Management Plan v1 (D5.1)** completed.
- **Preliminary Conceptual Framework (D5.14)** and draft **Monitoring Plan**.
- Expert workshops and consultations.
- Drafts of action plans for:
 - Use of decision support tools (DST),
 - Data infrastructure design,
 - Ex-ante project monitoring.

5. Data Strategy and Monitoring Components

- **Supply-demand analysis** for monitoring efforts.
- Development of **harmonised methods and guidelines**.
- Integration of inputs from other WPs (e.g., performance assessment, policy, communication).
- Emphasis on **citizen science** and **participatory monitoring** in future phases.

6. Soil Health within Agroecology

- Soil health is both a **core component and performance indicator** of agroecological systems.
- AE practices seek to:
 - Manage **organic matter**,
 - Enhance **biological activity**,
 - Improve **ecosystem functions** linked to soils.

Agroecology-soil health links are tracked via:

- **Implementation of soil-related AE principles**, and
- **Assessment of their sustainability impacts** across levels and timelines.

7. Outlook (2025–2033): Strategic Priorities

- Rollout of **prioritized data collection strategies**.
- Establishment of a **centralised database of agroecological indicators**.
- **Real-time formative evaluation** of funded projects.
- Integration with **Farm Sustainability Data Network** and other EU datasets.
- Development of **governance models** for monitoring platforms.
- Expansion of **interoperable infrastructures**.

Additional focus areas:

- Economic potential of agroecology,
- Monitoring of dietary patterns and sustainability.

Take-Home Messages

- Agroecological transition monitoring requires **coherent, harmonized, and multi-scale frameworks**.
- **Soil health is a foundational element** within the broader agroecology assessment logic.
- WP5 supports both **scientific evaluation** and **policy relevance** through robust data structures, participatory tools, and continuous stakeholder engagement.

5.2. Overview of the pilot session 2 lectures contents

Session 2.1. - Digital Tools for Soil Health Monitoring – 20 June 2025 Evaluation of the Impact of CAP

Lecture 1. Evaluation of the Impact of CAP Measures on Soil Organic Carbon in Spain

Presenter: José L. Gabriel

Objective: To evaluate the effect of **CAP (Common Agricultural Policy)** eco-scheme measures on **Soil**

Organic Carbon (SOC) in Spanish agricultural soils, through a structured national monitoring system and field data collection.

1. Relevance of Soil Organic Carbon (SOC)

Soil degradation concerns:

- Declining **SOC** linked to loss of **soil fertility** (P, N depletion),
- Increased **erosion and compaction**,
- Contribution to **climate change** via C emissions.

Policy context:

- **Soil Monitoring Law** and **LUCAS** module integration.
- **EU Regulation 2021/2115**: strategic orientation of the 2023–2027 CAP.
- SOC conservation is central to **sustainability and mitigation** strategies.

2. CAP 2023–2027 & Spanish Eco-schemes

Spain's CAP implementation includes eco-schemes directly linked to SOC:

Crop Systems	Practices
Annual crops	Direct sowing, cover crops, crop rotation
Woody crops	Pruning cover, living cover
Grasslands	Sustainable mowing, extensive grazing
All systems	Preservation of non-productive areas

Three thematic axes: **Low-carbon agriculture, Agroecology, Extensive systems**

3. AGRIAMBIO Collaboration

A research platform aiding CAP evaluation:

- Three thematic clusters: **Biodiversity, Social Equity, Soil Organic Carbon**.
- Tasks include data collection, analysis, training, and dissemination.

4. Design of the Spanish SOC Monitoring Network

Commissioned by: Spanish Ministry of Agriculture

Structure:

- **20,000 segments (10x10 km grid)**; ~630,000 plots.
- **8,000 segments selected** where crops occupy >15% surface.
- **Two farms per segment** selected based on predefined assignment rules.
- **Stratification criteria**: crop type, management system, CAP aid types.

Data sources:

- **ESYRCE, RSU, SIGPAC** for crop/aid history and geolocation since 2010.

5. Soil Sampling Methodology

- Based on the **LUCAS model**.
- **Sampling point per farm**, two depths: **0–10 cm** and **10–30 cm**.
- Each depth: 4 subsamples, homogenized and compacted.
- **~32,000 total samples** from 8,000 segments.

Quality controls included checks on compaction, cleanliness, extraction, and levelling.

6. Preliminary Results

15,892 farms sampled across 4 groups:

- Group 1: 33%
- Group 2: 26%
- Group 3: 9%
- Group 4: 32%

Comparisons conducted:

- **Grassland vs Arable land**
- **Practices with SOC benefit vs neutral or degrading practices**
- **Mapping of sampled vs non-sampled plots**

Results still **preliminary**, some samples pending lab analysis.

7. Next Steps

- Complete **lab analysis**: SOC and bulk density.
- Estimate **sequestration/emission factors** by year and practice.
- Integrate into:
 - National **SOC stock cartography**,
 - **IPCC inventories**,
 - **Carbon credit systems**.
- Expand monitoring to include additional parameters.

Take-Home Messages

- Spain is implementing a **robust, stratified, and geo-referenced SOC monitoring network** aligned with CAP eco-schemes.

- This effort supports **evidence-based policymaking, climate mitigation, and sustainable soil management.**
- Monitoring results will feed into **national reporting, IPCC inventories, and potentially voluntary carbon markets.**

Lecture 2. Possible contribution of remote sensing to soil monitoring.

Authors: Pierre Renault

Objective: To assess the potential of **remote sensing (RS)** and **digital soil mapping (DSM)** technologies as cost-effective, scalable, and data-rich alternatives or complements to traditional soil monitoring, within the context of the **EU Soil Monitoring Law (SML).**

1. Background: The Importance and Degradation of Soils

- Soils are crucial for **SDGs** via their role in:
 - Biomass production,
 - Carbon storage,
 - Water regulation,
 - Biodiversity support (over 25% of Earth's species),
 - Infrastructure stability and cultural value.
- Soil degradation is **rapid and multi-faceted**: erosion, sealing, compaction, salinization, nutrient loss, etc.
- Pedogenesis is slow: centuries to form 1 cm of soil.

2. Challenges in Traditional Soil Monitoring & Mapping

- **Laboratory-based monitoring** is expensive, infrequent, and spatially sparse.
- **Conventional mapping (DMSV)** is qualitative, expert-based, and lacks reproducibility.
- Need for **higher spatial resolution, quantitative data, temporal frequency, and uncertainty quantification.**

3. Potential of Remote Sensing for Soil Monitoring

Sensors & Platforms

- **Passive sensors:** multispectral (e.g. Sentinel-2), hyperspectral (VNIR), thermal IR, γ -ray spectrometry.
- **Active sensors:** radar (e.g. Sentinel-1 SAR), LiDAR.
- **Platforms:** satellites, airborne systems, UAVs.

Capabilities

- Detection of **SOC, moisture, texture**, and indirect assessment via **vegetation proxies.**
- **All-weather, high-frequency, and large-scale** data from SAR (vs. optical blockage by clouds).

- UAVs ideal for **high-resolution, local-scale** monitoring.

4. Data Access and Integration

- European and global access via:
 - **Copernicus Land Monitoring Services (CLMS)**,
 - **Theia, DINAMIS, ESA, NASA**,
 - **EUSO Dashboard** using MODIS, ASTER, IRS, etc.
- Open data platforms such as **Google Earth Engine** enhance accessibility.

5. Remote Sensing and Digital Soil Mapping (DSM)

Definition of DSM: DSM uses **numerical models** (e.g. SCORPAN) to predict spatial variation in soil properties using covariates such as RS data, terrain, land use, geology.

Key Models & Projects

- **SoilGrids (ISRIC), GlobalSoilMap, SCORPAN framework** ($s = f(S,C,O,R,P,A,N)$).
- **Tools:** machine learning (random forest, kriging), geostatistics, fuzzy logic, decision trees.

Validation & Uncertainty

- Validation through **cross-validation, expert review, and independent sampling**.
- Uncertainty mapping is essential for:
 - Decision-making reliability,
 - Sensitivity analysis,
 - Identifying gaps.

6. Limitations and Considerations

- RS mainly captures **surface properties** and is often limited by **vegetation cover**.
- Best results for bare soils or through **soil-vegetation coupled models**.
- RS variables often act as **covariates**, not direct measurements.

7. Examples of Application

- Mapping of **SOC, pH, texture, CaCO₃** using hyperspectral or multispectral imagery.
- Case studies using **temporal mosaics from Sentinel-1/2** to track soil dynamics.
- Integration with **DEM derivatives** and legacy soil maps for enhanced predictions.

8. Conclusions

- Traditional methods are essential but limited; **RS and DSM enable scalable, frequent, and quantitative monitoring**.

- RS allows the generation of **continuous spatial information** and **uncertainty layers** at resolutions compatible with **precision agriculture** and **environmental monitoring**.
- Future soil monitoring frameworks must **integrate remote sensing, model-based inference, and interdisciplinary data infrastructures**.

Take-Home Messages

- Remote sensing is a **transformative tool** for soil monitoring when combined with DSM.
- **Satellite data and UAV-based imagery** can support **cost-effective and timely** assessments of soil condition.
- DSM enables integration of heterogeneous data into **actionable, spatially explicit soil information**.
- These tools are vital for supporting the **implementation of the EU Soil Monitoring Law** and advancing sustainable soil management.

Session 2.2. - Digital Tools for Soil Health Monitoring – 20 June 2025 Evaluation of the Impact of CAP

Lecture 3. Decision-Support Tools for Soil Organic Carbon Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification: The MRV4SOC approach.

Marta Gómez-Giménez & Bertrand Guenet

Objectives of the Project

Develop and validate a **Tier 3 MRV framework** for **Soil Organic Carbon (SOC)**:

- **Quantify SOC accumulation** under carbon farming vs. conventional practices.
- Assess SOC response to **climate change and socio-economic drivers**.
- Deliver a **scalable, transparent, and cost-effective** MRV system to support **results-based payments** and **carbon markets**.

1. Project Structure

Six work packages:

- WP1: Coordination
- WP2: Data standardization
- WP3: GHG and C budgets
- WP4: Carbon markets integration
- WP5: MRV system integration
- WP6: Communication & support

2. Demonstration Sites

- **Countries:** Spain, Italy, Germany, Belgium, Czech Republic (+ Norway)
- **Biogeographic regions:** Mediterranean, Atlantic, Continental, Boreal, Arctic-Alpine
- **Land use types:** Cropland, grassland, forest, agroforestry, peatland, peri-urban

3. Model Inputs and Boundary Conditions

Data Sources

- **In-situ data:** Field measurements, soil samples, crop/management records
- **Remote Sensing (RS):**
 - Indicators of **aboveground biomass (AGB)** and **net primary productivity (NPP)** using the CASA model.
 - Sensors and satellite platforms used to substitute or complement in-situ data for upscaling.

4. Modelling Approach

Tier 3 Process-Based Model: RothC

- Models SOC dynamics by decomposing organic C pools.
- Influenced by **temperature, moisture, and soil cover factors**.

Key Features

- **Monte Carlo simulations** used for **uncertainty propagation**.
- **Sensitivity analysis** to evaluate the relative contribution of inputs (clay, temperature, C inputs, etc.).
- **Scenario analysis:** Carbon farming scenarios (+20%, +50%, +150% inputs), also under **+5°C warming**.

5. Remote Sensing Contributions

- Key for defining **boundary conditions** at landscape scale.
- Helps bridge spatial gaps and reduce costs in traditional monitoring.
- RS products used as **covariates** for modelling rather than direct measurements.

6. Example: Lonzée Site (BE)

- Multi-year simulations (2013–2024).
- Uncertainty intervals used to determine significant SOC changes.
- Analysis of input relevance showed C inputs had **greatest impact**, followed by **temperature and clay**.

Take-Home Messages

- **Hybrid monitoring** combining in-situ and RS data is essential for **Tier 3 MRV**.

- SOC accumulation depends on **soil type, management, spatial scale, and climate**.
- **Process-based models** are valuable for scenario testing but require high-quality input data.
- **Uncertainty propagation** enhances **transparency** and **trust** in carbon market mechanisms.

Lecture 4. Soil monitoring strategies supporting the implementation of carbon farming practices for improving soil health in the Mediterranean and Southern Europe.

Presenter: Mercedes Román Dobarco

Purpose: To develop and implement soil monitoring protocols that support the evaluation of **Carbon Farming Practices (CFPs)** in Mediterranean and Southern Europe, through:

- Multi-actor Living Labs (LLs),
- Co-created soil sampling strategies,
- Integration of Digital Soil Mapping (DSM),
- Assessment of soil health and SOC baseline and changes.

1. Context & Justification

- Agriculture is a **major driver of SOC loss**, with an estimated **60–85 Pg of SOC lost from topsoils**.
- Increasing SOC through CFPs is a **cost-effective strategy** for:
 - **Climate change mitigation/adaptation,**
 - **Food security,**
 - **Soil degradation reversal,**
 - **Biodiversity conservation.**
- SOC responses are **site-dependent**: vary with **soil type, land use, and climate**.

2. Project Overview: LILAS4SOILS

- **60-month EU project (2024–2029)** with 5 Living Labs in 6 countries.
- Up to 100 demo-sites to test **19 Carbon Farming Practices**.
- Aims to:
 - Co-design CFPs adapted to **environmental and socio-economic contexts,**
 - Support **long-term adoption and MRV readiness,**
 - Foster **knowledge transfer and upscaling.**

3. Soil Monitoring Strategy

Soil Sampling Protocol

- Designed to **measure and re-measure** SOC and soil health indicators (2025–2028).
- **Not a standard MRV protocol**, but a **flexible guide** for Living Labs.
- Data used to:
 - Set **baseline SOC stock (Time 0),**

- Model SOC dynamics,
- Quantify CFP effects,
- Explore **synergies between SOC and other soil functions.**

4. Statistical Sampling Design

Approaches Considered:

- **Design-based:** for estimating mean SOC stock.
- **Model-based:** for spatial prediction and mapping.

Techniques Used:

- **Stratified random sampling** using **compact geographical strata.**
- Stratification based on:
 - **Soil type, slope, TWI, clay %, NDVI time series,** land use, SOC maps.
- **Static-synchronous space-time design:**
 - Same units revisited → improves precision with fewer samples.
 - Balances spatial and temporal resolution.

Challenges:

- High SOC variability → requires high sampling density.
- Trade-off between **cost, scale, and confidence.**
- Larger aggregated areas improve **accuracy and cost-efficiency.**

5. Digital Soil Mapping (DSM) Integration

- SOC monitoring is enhanced by **DSM and SCORPAN-based covariates** (soil, climate, organisms, relief, etc.).
- **Use of satellite time series, DEMs, gamma radiometrics,** etc.
- Incorporation of **Pedogenon and Phenosoil mapping** to define **SOC baselines** and **soil health zones.**

Applications:

- Inform **baseline setting** for MRV.
- Support **targeted implementation** of CFPs.
- Develop **Soil Health Assessment Maps** with contextual thresholds.

6. SOC Fraction Mapping

- SOC is subdivided into:
 - **MAOC:** mineral-associated organic carbon,
 - **POC:** particulate organic carbon,
 - **PyOC:** pyrogenic organic carbón.

- These fractions are used to assess:
 - **SOC vulnerability,**
 - **Response to warming or management,**
 - **Optimization of practices** based on SOC stabilization potential.

Take-Home Messages

- **Sustainable soil management** via carbon farming has the potential to enhance both **soil health** and **climate resilience**.
- There is no universal best sampling strategy—**site-specific approaches** integrating **environmental covariates** and **prior data** are most effective.
- **DSM is essential** to efficiently guide monitoring, enhance MRV design, and inform **evidence-based soil policy** in Southern Europe.

6. Feedback and Evaluation of the pilot sessions implementation

6.1. Registered participants and attendees profiles

For the purposes of this section's analysis, all registered participants are considered pilot audience. Not all pre-registered participants attended the live online training sessions. However, all participants had access to the training resources and evaluation forms for individual and deferred use beyond the live session.

Session 1 (13 June 2025)

Session 1 of the training program “Supporting Capacity Building in Soil Monitoring in Europe”, scheduled for 13 June 2025 reached a figure of **117 registered participants**, reflecting strong interest in training related to soil monitoring and the upcoming SML.

Geographical representation

The geographical distribution was diverse, with significant participation from countries such as Spain, Italy, and Germany, which host a large number of European soil health initiatives. Spain recorded the highest number of registrations, accounting for approximately 35% of the total, followed by Italy (19%) and Ukraine (6%). Other countries such as Belgium, Germany, Hungary, and Portugal also contributed with smaller shares ranging between 3% and 4%. This diversity highlights the pan-European scope of the event and the shared relevance of the topic across different national contexts (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution by professional category of registered participants in Session 1 (13 June 2025)

Professional categories

Regarding participants' professional backgrounds, 50% came from academia and research institutions, reinforcing the technical and scientific focus of the training content. 20% of attendees selected the "Other" category, which included consultants, NGO representatives, and staff from multilateral organisations. Additionally, 14% represented regional public administrations and 8% came from national administrations, indicating the interest from different levels of government responsible for implementing the legislation. Finally, 4% identified as implementation technicians and another 4% as representatives from EU bodies, underlining both the operational and institutional dimensions of the course (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution by professional category of registered participants in Session 1 (13 June 2025)

Session 2 (20 June 2025)

Session 2 of the training program "Supporting Capacity Building in Soil Monitoring in Europe" scheduled for 20 June 2025 reached a figure of **139 registered participants**, confirming the sustained interest in the topic of soil health and the use of digital tools for its monitoring.

Geographical representation

Registrations came from a wide range of countries, with particularly strong representation from Spain, Italy, and Ukraine. This reflects the commitment of these nations to the development and implementation of advanced methodologies for monitoring soil health. Spain recorded the highest participation, accounting for 33% of registered participants, followed by Italy (19%) and Ukraine (9%). Other countries such as Germany (5%), Belgium (4%) and Austria, Hungary, Portugal, Denmark, and France (each with 3%) also contributed to the diversity of the audience. The involvement of countries from both Northern and Southern Europe brought valuable territorial and climatic diversity to the training (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Geographical distribution of registered participants in Session 2 (20 June 2025)

Professional categories:

Once again, the professional profile of participants was led by the academic and research sector, which accounted for 52% of the total. There was also significant participation from professionals in regional administrations (13%) and national administrations (6%), reflecting the growing interest of public authorities in integrating digital tools into their soil monitoring and reporting strategies. Other categories, such as “Other” (20%), implementation technicians (6%) and representatives from EU bodies (3%), contributed a complementary and operational perspective to the course discussions (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Geographical distribution of registered participants in Session 2 (20 June 2025)

Live participation

Although the number of registered participants was high for both sessions, the actual live connection data during the streaming were as follows:

- ✓ Session 1.1 (13 June): 70 participants connected
- ✓ Session 1.2 (13 June): 60 participants connected
- ✓ Session 2.1 (20 June): 62 participants connected
- ✓ Session 2.2 (20 June): 55 participants connected

These figures reflect a live attendance rate of between 47% and 60% relative to total registrations, As indicated, we consider for this analyses all the pre-registered participants as pilot audience, since the recorded sessions and assessment survey are available for all the registered attendances.

6.2. Participants assessment of the training

After each of one the pilot sessions, a participatory consultation was carried out using the *Mentimeter* platform in order to collect the pilot attendances feedback about satisfaction with content, usefulness and methodology.

Session 1.1: Innovating Soil Monitoring: From Indicators to Policy Impact (13 June 2025)

Session 1.1, was held on 13 June 2025 with 70 participants connected. It featured presentations by Grzegorz Siebielec and Agnieszka Klimkowicz-Pawlas (IUNG, Poland) on key soil monitoring indicators and by Claire Chenu (INRAE, France) on soil health monitoring in the context of the forthcoming European Soil Directive. At the end of the session, a participant evaluation survey was conducted, the results of which are summarized below.

Participant profile

The survey received 36 responses (51% of participants). Most respondents came from academia or research institutions (58%) and public administrations (28% in total, mainly regional authorities). Regarding geographic origin, Spain accounted for the largest share of responses (around 42%), with a total of 15 European countries represented.

Quantitative assessment of the session

- **Usefulness of the session:** 39% rated the session as “very useful” and 57% as “useful”; no participant rated it negatively (i.e., “not very useful” or “not useful at all”).
- **Relevance:** 52% found the content “very relevant” and 33% “quite relevant” to their work (15% “somewhat relevant”; 0% “not relevant”).
- **Applicability:** 52% stated they could apply what they learned with some adaptation, 19% could do so immediately, and 30% “maybe in the future”; no respondent indicated that the content would not be applicable.
- **Knowledge gain:** Before the session, 55% had medium-level knowledge of the topic, 22% high, 17% low, and 3% very high. After the session, 52% reported a “moderate” improvement in their

capacity, and 26% reported a “significant” improvement; the rest indicated a slight improvement or chose “cannot assess yet.”

- **Recommendation:** 100% of respondents would recommend this training to colleagues (52% definitely and 30% very likely would; the remainder probably would).

Qualitative comments from participants

Participants identified both technical aspects of monitoring and their link to policy as the most valuable parts of the session. Many highlighted the selection and justification of key indicators presented by IUNG, including the comparison between national networks and the European LUCAS sampling scheme. Claire Chenu’s overview of soil health in the context of the new European directive was also highly appreciated – particularly her proposals on biological indicators and sampling strategies. As one participant noted, “all the presentations were very interesting and important,” reflecting a high level of overall satisfaction with the content.

Regarding future needs, participants proposed a range of topics for further exploration. These included practical examples of how the new SML could be implemented in different countries, defining thresholds for indicators tailored to regional conditions, and developing standardised measurement methods and sampling strategies according to land use types. Several comments stressed the importance of considering regional/pedoclimatic differences (e.g., Mediterranean vs. Alpine contexts), improving data access and the use of modelling tools, and strengthening public communication and awareness about soil importance. One participant summarised this shared concern by asking: “How do we determine which parameters are most important for different regions? All soils matter.”

Session 1.2: Innovating Soil Monitoring: From Indicators to Policy Impact (13 June 2025)

Session 1.2, was held on 13 June 2025, with approximately 60 participants connected. The session featured presentations by Adolfo Perdomo on the Soil Quality Index (SQI) and José M. Ávila on an agroecological monitoring framework. At the end of the session, a participant evaluation survey was conducted, the results of which are summarised below.

Participant profile

The survey received 51 responses (around 85% of connected participants). Most respondents came from academia or research institutions (55%), followed by regional (22%) and national (6%) administrations, along with other profiles (16%), including monitoring technicians. In terms of geographic origin, approximately 50% were from Spain, with participants also coming from 11 other European countries, reflecting a diverse international audience.

Quantitative results of the evaluation

The quantitative evaluation of the session was highly positive overall. Below is a summary of the closed questions and the distribution of responses (in percentage of participants who answered each question):

- **Prior knowledge:** Before the session, 54% rated their knowledge of the topic as medium, 22% high, 20% low, and 4% very high. This indicates that a large portion of the audience had limited or moderate initial knowledge of the subject.
- **Overall assessment of the session:** 89% rated the session as useful or very useful (47% and 42%, respectively), 8% found it acceptable, and only 3% (one participant) considered it not very useful. This reflects a high overall level of satisfaction with the session.
- **Relevance to professional context:** 84% indicated that the content was very or quite relevant to their work (49% very relevant, 35% quite relevant), 14% found it somewhat relevant, and only ~3% not relevant at all. Therefore, the vast majority perceived the session as pertinent to their professional field.
- **Applicability of the content:** Nearly 70% of respondents intended to apply the knowledge gained (21.6% immediately and 48.6% with some adaptation), while the remaining 30% said they “might in the future.” No participant dismissed its applicability, suggesting the content has real potential for use in diverse contexts.
- **Knowledge and capacity improvement:** 81% reported that the session improved their ability to contribute to soil monitoring either moderately or significantly (59.5% moderately, 21.6% significantly). Another 10.8% reported a slight improvement, ~5% were not yet able to assess it, and only one participant (~3%) saw no improvement. These results show a clear formative impact on most attendees.
- **Recommendation of the training:** Enthusiasm for the session is reflected in the fact that ~84% of respondents would recommend this type of training to a colleague (54.1% definitely, 29.7% very likely). An additional 13.5% would probably recommend it, and only 2.7% (one participant) would not. In sum, nearly all participants rated the session positively and worth sharing.

Qualitative comments from participants

In the open-ended questions, participants highlighted several specific aspects of the presentations they found most useful or interesting. Many comments referred to the first presentation by Adolfo Perdomo on the Soil Quality Index (SQI). For example, one participant noted that “soil monitoring indicators and the SQI” were the most valuable part of the session, and several appreciated the inclusion of biological indicators in the SQI. The second presentation by José M. Ávila on the agroecological conceptual framework was praised for its clarity; according to one attendee, “the structuring of the numerous parameters in the second presentation” made the approach easier to understand. Overall, “both presentations were excellent,” according to several respondents, combining a practical perspective (SQI applied to a real case) with a strategic vision (monitoring plan for the agroecological transition) in a complementary way. This alignment between delivered content and audience expectations was also reflected in the high quantitative scores mentioned.

Respondents also offered constructive suggestions for future sessions. Among the most recurrent proposals were: including more practical examples and case studies to deepen the real-world application of the concepts; providing detailed guidance on how to calculate and select an appropriate SQI for different contexts; conducting longitudinal soil data tracking (to identify trends and long-term effects); placing greater emphasis on soil microbiology in relation to agroecology; and encouraging increased participation from farmers and citizens in monitoring initiatives. These suggestions reflect

the audience's interest in even more practical, long-term, and participatory content, which can help shape future training design.

Conclusions

In conclusion, Session 1.2 *"Innovating Soil Monitoring: From Indicators to Policy Impact"* had a very positive impact on participants, according to the collected evaluation. The combination of a practical tool (SQI) with an innovative conceptual framework was well received, resulting in high scores for usefulness and relevance. Participants not only valued the content delivered by Adolfo Perdomo and José M. Ávila but also reported gaining knowledge and practical capacity. The feedback suggests that future workshops should further explore practical cases and maintain participatory approaches to continue improving the effectiveness and impact of soil monitoring training.

Session 2.1. - Digital Tools for Soil Health Monitoring – 20 June 2025

Session 2.1 was held on 20 June 2025, with 62 participants connected. The session featured presentations by José Luis Gabriel (INIA-CSIC, Spain) on the assessment of CAP measures' impact on soil organic carbon (SOC) and Pierre Renault (INRAE, France) on the contribution of remote sensing to soil monitoring. At the end of the session, a participant evaluation survey was conducted, the results of which are summarised below.

Participant profile

The survey received 22 responses (around 35% of connected participants). Most respondents came from academia or research institutions, regional and national administrations, and technical staff working in soil monitoring. In terms of geographic distribution, the audience included participants from Spain and several other European countries, reflecting an international and multidisciplinary profile.

Quantitative results of the evaluation

- **Prior knowledge:** Before the session, 18% of respondents reported low knowledge, 50% medium, 23% high, and 9% very high. In total, about 68% had limited prior knowledge on digital tools for soil monitoring.
- **Overall session rating:** All respondents rated the session as either "useful" or "very useful"; 62.5% selected "useful" and 37.5% "very useful." No participant rated it negatively.
- **Professional relevance:** 56% rated the content as "very relevant" and 38% as "quite relevant" to their work; only ~6% rated it as "somewhat relevant," and no one found it irrelevant.
- **Applicability:** 50% stated they could apply the knowledge gained in the future, and 44% said they could do so with some adaptation. Only 6% were unsure, and no participant indicated it would not be useful.
- **Improvement of capacities:** 25% reported a significant improvement in their ability to contribute to soil monitoring, 50% a moderate improvement, and 25% a slight improvement. No participant reported no improvement.
- **Recommendation:** 100% of respondents would recommend this type of training to colleagues. Specifically, 50% would "definitely" recommend it, 37% would "very likely" recommend it, and 13% would "possibly" do so.

Qualitative comments from participants

Participants highlighted a variety of valuable aspects of the session. The remote sensing and digital soil mapping segment presented by Dr. Renault was particularly appreciated, as were the practical examples related to the CAP shared by Dr. Gabriel in the Spanish context. One participant noted the “comparison between conventional methods and remote sensing of SOC” as particularly insightful, while another praised “the practical examples presented, especially the case from Spain.” Several respondents mentioned the SCORPAN model and Digital Soil Mapping (DSM), emphasising the usefulness of integrating remote sensing data into soil property maps. Others highlighted the availability of new datasets and the presentation of a global soil map, as well as insights into the Spanish national soil monitoring network and its sampling strategy. Some respondents commented that “everything was interesting,” suggesting both presentations were well aligned and complementary, resonating with participants’ interests.

Participants shared a range of constructive suggestions for upcoming sessions:

- **Advanced digital tools:** Requests were made for more “hands-on” training on the use of remote sensing data for soil health, including how to access and analyse it. There was also interest in exploring new technologies such as AI and machine learning for soil monitoring.
- **Standardization and data:** Respondents suggested addressing strategies to harmonise soil monitoring frameworks across Europe, integrating national schemes with the new EU framework (including the forthcoming Soil Health Law). This includes unifying sampling protocols and methodologies, defining common thresholds for soil health indicators, and sharing tools to convert or compare metrics across programmes. Other recommendations included enhancing data management, building shared soil databases, and addressing data protection (GDPR) in monitoring systems.
- **Soil organic carbon and biological processes:** Participants expressed interest in learning more about how to effectively and permanently improve SOC, including exploring tools for increasing SOC levels, the role of microbial processes in carbon sequestration, and strategies to promote beneficial biological activity in soils.
- **Farmer-oriented approaches:** There was a strong call to integrate the perspective of end users, such as farmers. Participants suggested discussing the practical benefits for farmers of engaging in soil monitoring, and how they could use soil health data in the field. Some also proposed exploring participatory research methodologies led by farmers, allowing them to carry out trials or actively contribute to soil health monitoring.

Conclusions

The evaluation results reflect a very positive perception of Session 2.1. All participants found it useful and relevant to their professional activities, and all would recommend similar training. This overwhelmingly favourable feedback is linked to the session content, which effectively met expectations by combining national practical examples with innovative digital tools. Most respondents with limited prior knowledge (68%) reported clear improvements in their skills after the training. In summary, the mix of field-level policy measures and monitoring technology made the session highly

useful and immediately relevant, while laying a solid foundation for future sessions to explore the proposed topics in more depth.

Session 2.2. - Digital Tools for Soil Health Monitoring – 20 June 2025

Session 2.2 was held on 20 June 2025, with 55 participants connected. The session featured presentations by Marta Gómez and Bertrand Guenet (MRV4SOC, Spain/France) on MRV tools for soil carbon monitoring, and Miguel Román (CSIC, Spain) on soil carbon monitoring approaches and national case studies. At the end of the session, a participant evaluation survey was conducted, the results of which are summarised below.

Participant profile

The survey received **22 responses** (approximately **40%** of connected participants). Most respondents came from **research institutions, public administrations, and technical experts involved in soil data collection and monitoring**. Geographically, the majority were based in **Spain**, with additional participants from other **European countries**, contributing to a diverse and multidisciplinary audience.

Quantitative results

- **Prior knowledge:** At the beginning of the session, 50% of participants reported a medium level of prior knowledge, 23% a high level, and 9% a very high level (the remaining respondents indicated a low level).
- **Overall evaluation:** 62.5% rated the session as “useful” and 37.5% as “very useful”.
- **Relevance:** 56% found the content to be “very relevant” and 38% “quite relevant” to their professional work.
- **Applicability:** 44% stated that they would be able to apply the knowledge acquired (with adaptations), while 50% said they “might apply it in the future”.
- **Capacity improvement:** 50% reported a moderate improvement in their ability to contribute to soil monitoring, 25% a significant improvement, and 25% a slight improvement.
- **Recommendation:** 50% would definitely recommend this type of training, and 37.5% would very likely do so.

Qualitative comments

Participants particularly highlighted the practical content on remote sensing and digital soil mapping. For instance, “soil sampling procedures” and “hands-on approaches to remote sensing” were especially valued. The explanation of predictive models (e.g. the “SCORPAN model”), available databases, and case studies from Spain also received positive feedback. One participant specifically mentioned “the sampling design and strategy in the Spanish case study” as particularly useful content.

Suggestions for future sessions included:

- Applying **Artificial Intelligence** and **Machine Learning** to soil monitoring.
- Defining **thresholds for soil health indicators** and harmonising monitoring procedures across countries.
- **Integrating national monitoring frameworks** into the new European soil monitoring scheme (including data protection – GDPR – and sharing of national soil databases).
- Including **practical case studies** on improving soil organic carbon (e.g. working with farmers) and further exploring **remote sensing approaches**.

These comments reflect a strong interest in advanced digital tools (e.g. machine learning, GIS), practical applications, and international harmonisation in future training sessions.

Conclusions

The evaluation results reflect a positive perception of the session: most participants found the content relevant and applicable to their professional context. The high relevance and willingness to recommend the training align with the interest expressed in the digital technologies presented (remote sensing, modelling). Overall, participants found the session useful for their work in soil monitoring and suggested further emphasis on practical and technological aspects in future workshops.

7. Lessons learned and Conclusions

7.1. Challenges faced, lessons learned and potential improvement points

- **Legislative uncertainty and change of approach:** One of the main challenges was that the SML had not yet been finalised during the implementation of the project. This created an initial dilemma: should the training program wait for the final adoption of the directive to be developed, or should it proceed based on the available information? The decision was to act proactively. The training was built on solid foundations, including recognised scientific knowledge and technical practices, designed to be useful with or without the legal framework, while leaving space to add specific legal elements once the text was finalised. This approach involved reorganising the training sequence into a layered learning format and ensuring that the programme had immediate relevance within existing policy frameworks such as the CAP and environmental strategies. As a result, the task was able to move forward independently of political timelines while remaining ready to incorporate the legal details agreed upon in 2025.
- **Balancing broad coverage with depth and up-to-date content:** Another challenge was defining which content to include in the training. Soil monitoring is a broad topic, covering physical, chemical, and biological aspects, as well as different land uses such as agriculture, forestry, and urban areas, and including issues such as contamination. Moreover, the field was constantly evolving during the project. For example, there were updates at the EU level concerning proposed indicators for soil biodiversity. The difficulty lay in creating a curriculum that was both comprehensive enough to cover the main components of the SML and concrete and current enough to remain relevant. The strategy to address this was prioritisation and continuous updating. Through the needs assessment and expert feedback, critical areas were identified (based on eight categories from the internal document), while secondary or redundant topics were excluded. From the beginning, the training included the latest scientific and regulatory developments, such as harmonised monitoring methods, findings from ongoing projects, and references to related legislative proposals like the Nature Restoration Law. Dialogue with the EC helped to focus the content on what countries would truly need, while input from PREPSOIL WP5 ensured no essential elements were overlooked. This approach led to a curriculum that was both current and relevant.
- **Different audience profiles:** The target audience for the training was highly heterogeneous, ranging from laboratory technicians to policy-makers. This presented a pedagogical challenge: how to make the training useful for everyone without it being too basic for some or too technical for others. The solution was to segment needs by profile and structure content accordingly. The needs assessment had already classified priorities based on whether the target group was policy-makers, technical personnel, or data managers. In the curriculum design, each module contained components tailored to benefit specific profiles, while collectively building a shared understanding or “common language of soil”. Clear target groups were defined, including public staff responsible for data, decision-makers using that data, and the Living Labs community, to ensure examples and case studies reflected their realities. Workshop formats, such as mixed discussion tables, also promoted knowledge exchange between profiles, enriching the experience for all. This flexible approach helped overcome the challenge of heterogeneity, offering value both to analytical

technicians (who deepened their knowledge of methods and indicators) and to managers (who explored implications for policy design and use of information).

- **Multi-actor collaboration and external validation:** An important organisational challenge was coordinating the diverse range of actors involved in co-creation, including EU projects, national institutions, and the EC. Integrating different perspectives required time and coordination efforts but was considered essential to legitimise and enhance the quality of the training content.
- **Time constraints and pilot workshops:** The final phase of the project involved implementing and evaluating the pilot workshops within a limited timeframe (first half of 2025), while also finalising the conclusions before the project ended. Coordinating pan-European participation in June 2025 and collecting useful feedback under time pressure was a logistical and methodological challenge. The solution was to carefully plan the pilots as structured test runs. Success indicators were defined, and evaluation tools were prepared in advance so that feedback from each session — including participant satisfaction and learning outcomes — could be processed immediately. Evaluations were also monitored continuously to enable real-time adjustments. For instance, the short interval between Session 1 and Session 2 allowed for the incorporation of small improvements based on initial feedback. This agile feedback loop ensured that by the end of June, a clear list of improvements to be incorporated into the final curriculum was available. In addition, the project included the preparation of a post-pilot report compiling all evaluations, which informed the final version of the training. In short, despite tight deadlines, the proactive and quality-focused approach enabled the pilot workshops to be used to their full potential, becoming a critical step to ensure the long-term success of the training programme.

7.2. Conclusions and next steps (legacy and future applications)

The work conducted under Task 5.4 of the PREPSOIL project has laid a solid foundation for the design and implementation of training programs on soil health monitoring and indicators, in alignment with the objectives of the EU Mission Soil. The identification of training needs has been particularly thorough and inclusive, shaped by a wide-ranging consultation process that reflects the diversity of actors and initiatives engaged in soil health across Europe. Importantly, this needs assessment is conceived as a living instrument, comprehensive in its current form yet open to refinement in light of future strategic developments. A key upcoming decision will be whether to focus training efforts more narrowly in support of the forthcoming EU SML or to maintain a broader scope aligned with the wider objectives of the EU Mission Soil. This distinction will have significant implications for both the content and the target audiences of future training initiatives.

Within the current task, the development and delivery of a pilot training program represented a strategic effort to test formats and content while fostering engagement and gathering practical feedback. A deliberate decision was made to focus the pilot sessions on a selected number of topics considered both timely and transferable. These were delivered through a mixed-format program that emphasized knowledge sharing and the exchange of best practices. The sessions successfully combined general training content with practical case studies and real-world examples/practices, demonstrating how concepts and methodologies could be adapted to diverse territorial contexts

within the EU. This pilot approach benefitted greatly from the participation of a diverse group of experts and practitioners, including representatives from other Mission Soil projects, whose contributions enriched the content and grounded the discussions in applied experience.

A central dimension of Task 5.4 has been the emphasis on collaboration, dialogue and the creation of synergies with other projects and stakeholders involved in the EU Mission Soil. This collaborative approach has proven both fruitful and essential. One of the distinctive features and enduring challenges of the Mission Soil is the need for coherence, complementarity and mutual reinforcement across a growing ecosystem of projects. In this respect, the activities under Task 5.4 were designed with three main objectives in mind:

- To build upon and valorize existing knowledge and avoid duplication
- To capitalize on the momentum and findings of previous efforts (such as EJP Soil) while ensuring continuity with future initiatives that may outlast PREPSOIL
- To align with other Mission Soil projects that are developing or testing monitoring frameworks in real-world environments such as LLs.

This approach enhances the potential for scalability, integration and policy relevance.

Looking ahead, the possibilities for shaping and expanding a comprehensive training program on soil health monitoring are wide-ranging. These depend not only on alignment with EU strategic frameworks (such as the SML), but also on several practical considerations, including:

- The specific professional profiles or stakeholder groups targeted
- The timeframes and resources available for delivery
- The desired degree of interactivity and participatory engagement
- The preferred structure (e.g., sequential modules versus stand-alone sessions)
- The level of involvement of EU institutions (such as the JRC) versus external partners (such as PREPSOIL or other Horizon-funded projects)
- Whether to deliver training at national level, tailored to specific country contexts, or at a multi-territorial level to foster cross-border learning and alignment of practices

The outputs of Task 5.4 represent a significant contribution and a valuable resource base for the EC and the broader community working on soil health. This task delivers not only an overview of key training needs and priorities, but also a robust set of raw materials for further development. These include:

- A elaborated, discussed and expandable list of relevant training topics
- An initial registry of potential target groups and interested participants
- A pilot training program focused on selected priority themes, complete with corresponding training materials and supporting documentation

Although limited in scope, the pilot was designed with transferability in mind and can serve as a blueprint for more extensive and tailored programs across the EU.

In conclusion, this task provides essential groundwork for future capacity-building efforts under the EU Mission Soil. The work conducted demonstrates both the immediate value and the long-term potential of structured, collaborative and strategically aligned training initiatives. Building on the achievements and lessons of this task, future steps can now focus on consolidating a shared training architecture, flexible enough to adapt to evolving policy and stakeholder needs, yet coherent enough to support the common goals of soil health monitoring and improvement across Europe. With the right coordination and investment, this training program can become a key instrument in enabling the systemic transformation envisioned by the EU Mission Soil.

Annexes

Annex 1. Programmes of the pilot sessions (detailed agendas of each workshop)

Session 1.1. - Innovating Soil Monitoring: From Indicators to Policy Impact – 13 June 2025

Time (CET)	PRESENTATION / TOPIC	INSTITUTION	SPEAKER
10h00 – 10h10	Introduction	INIA – CSIC (Spain)	Mr. Pablo Gómez and Mr. José Luis Pita-Romero
10h10 – 10h50	Lecture 1. Key indicators and their complexity. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key physical, chemical and biological indicators and their importance. • Indicators proposed in the Soil Monitoring Law. • The need for flexible approaches that consider regional particularities and land uses. 	Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation - IUNG (Poland)	Mr. Grzegorz Siebielec and Mrs. Agnieszka Klimkowicz- Pawlas
10h50 – 11h00	Questions and Answers (Q&A)		
11h00 – 11h40	Lecture 2. Monitoring Soil Health in the framework of the future EU Soil Directive. Lessons learned and recommendations from EJP SOIL. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harmonized monitoring is essential. • Sampling strategy matters. • A tiered system of biological indicators is proposed. • Setting realistic and adaptable targets is crucial. • Data management must support open access and policy use. 	INRAE (France) & EJP SOIL	Mrs. Claire Chenu
11h40 – 11h55	Questions and Answers (Q&A)		
11h55 – 12h00	Evaluation Questionnaire		

Session 1.2. - Innovating Soil Monitoring: From Indicators to Policy Impact

Time	PRESENTATION / TOPIC	INSTITUTION	SPEAKER
12h00 – 12h45	<p>Lecture 3. Soil Monitoring Indicators and the SQI: A Practical Approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of a set of 40 soil monitoring indicators, with emphasis on the most relevant for Soil Quality Index (SQI). • Introduction of the SQI as a tool to integrate, interpret, and communicate monitoring results. • Explanation of how to build an ad-hoc SQI, including indicator selection and scoring functions ("more is better", "less is better", "optimum"). • Application of the SQI in a real case study in a desertified area (Lanzarote, Canary Islands), showing its correlation with microbial and faunal biodiversity indicators. 	University of La Laguna (Spain)	Mr. Adolfo Perdomo
12h45 – 13h00	Questions and Answers (Q&A)		
13h00 – 13h30	<p>Lecture 4. Building the conceptual framework for monitoring agroecological transition</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introducing the Agroecology Partnership and its monitoring approach. • Introduction to the Monitoring Plan and the conceptual framework to support evidence-based policy and practice in agroecology. • Connecting with soil monitoring initiatives. 	Agroecology Partnership & LifeWatch ERIC ICT Core (Spain)	Mr. José Manuel Avila
13h30 – 13h45	Questions and Answers (Q&A)		
13h45 – 14:00	Evaluation Questionnaire		

Session 2.1. - Digital Tools for Soil Health Monitoring – 20 June 2025

Time (CET)	PRESENTATION / TOPIC	INSTITUTION	SPEAKER
10h00 – 10h15	Introduction	INIA – CSIC (Spain)	Mr. Pablo Gómez and Mr. José Luis Pita
10h15 – 10h50	<p>Lecture 1. Evaluation of the Impact of CAP Measures on Soil Organic Carbon in Spain.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increasing SOC in agricultural systems is urgent. The actual SOC improvements from certain practices need to be confirmed at the farm level. The Spanish Ministry is conducting a large-scale validation of SOC improvements. Preliminary data supports the improvements and helps define the expected range of carbon sequestration. 	INIA – CSIC (Spain)	Mr. José Luis Gabriel
10h50 – 11h00	Questions and Answers (Q&A)		
11h00 – 11h30	<p>Lecture 2. Possible contribution of remote sensing to soil monitoring.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Although necessary, traditional or conventional soil monitoring methods based on in situ observations or soil sampling are costly, provide estimates with low spatial and temporal resolution, and offer no information on uncertainties outside the characterized sites. Remote sensing provides direct access to certain soil information or makes soil property covariates available, with potentially very high spatial resolution and revisit frequency. By integrating soil data with other sources, including remote sensing, digital soil mapping enables the production of accurate property maps, as well as associated uncertainty maps. 	INRAE (France)	Dr. Pierre RENAULT
11h30 – 11h45	Questions and Answers (Q&A)		
11h45 – 12h00	Evaluation Questionnaire		

Session 2.2. - Digital Tools for Soil Health Monitoring – 20 June 2025

Time	PRESENTATION / TOPIC	INSTITUTION	SPEAKER
12h00 – 12h45	<p>Lecture 3. Decision-Support Tools for Soil Organic Carbon Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification: The MRV4SOC approach.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hybrid monitoring systems integrating in-situ and remote sensing data into process-based models are highlighted to build robust, transparent, and cost-effective Tier 3 MRV approaches. Simulated carbon sequestration depends on soil associations, spatial scales, management practices, and climate conditions. Process-based models can be an interesting alternative to test 'what-if' scenarios. The accuracy of model inputs has an impact on the performance of the model. Therefore, uncertainties must be propagated to increase robustness and transparency. 	GMV and French - MRV4SOC	Mrs. Marta Gómez (GMV) and Mr. Bertrand Guenet (CNRS)
12h45 – 13h00	Questions and Answers (Q&A)		
13h00 – 13h30	<p>Lecture 4. Soil monitoring strategies supporting the implementation of carbon farming practices for improving soil health in the Mediterranean and Southern Europe.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable soil management has the potential to contribute to climate change mitigation and adaptation while improving soil health, and hence food security and ecosystem functioning. There is no magic formula for finding the best sampling strategy, as often it is site-dependant. However, incorporating prior information on environmental covariates, soil type and spatial predictions of SOC generally improve sampling efficiency. Digital soil mapping is a powerful tool for supporting sustainable soil management and promoting soil security, from the field to global scale. 	NEIKER (Spain) - LILAS4SOILS	Mrs. Mercedes Román
13h30 – 13h45	Questions and Answers (Q&A)		
13h45 – 14:00	Evaluation Questionnaire		

Annex 2. Evaluation questionnaires and detailed results (feedback forms and collected data)

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Preparing the ground for healthy soils:
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PREPSOIL – 2022-2025

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

Soil monitoring	Lessons learned from the EJP SOIL	Everything	All
The key indicators	All	Soil compaction and erosion	The questions and talks at the end

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

Soil monitoring approximation	All contents were very interesting and important in general. But questions regarding the transfer functions still remain.	Lecture 1: key indicators	-
The differences between LUCAS and national monitoring systems	Soil indicators classification and selection	Report from national comparison	Comparison of national vs European (LUCAS) sampling

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

Key physical indicators	The comparison of lucas and smi data, that was interesting as well as the review of soil indicators, looking forward for the soil health index part in the coming talks	Report of national network comparison	All presentations were very interesting!
All, but Claire Chenu was very cutting edge	Indicators and the threshold	Soil Monitoring Law context and applying information	Data Management

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

The conversations about future and next steps	the soil indicators review	2de speaker Claire Chenu, target and threshold	Explain the soil indicators of the SML
Data Management	The whole session	All, but Claire Chenu was very cutting edge	The different types of soil indicators

HORIZON-MISS-2021-SOIL-01-01 /
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PREPSOIL – 2022-2025

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

Claire Chenu presentation EJP soil results	The choice of the right indicators according to land use, region, type of soil	Both presentations were excellent	Claire Chenu
Proposal of best soil health indicators	The indicators state of the art	Selection of indicators and rationale behind it. Sampling strategy selection and background information for determining threshold values for indicators	2de speaker Claire Chenu - target and threshold

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

Key indicators and monitoring approaches studies	Policy implementation	The first one was very well structured	Key indicator
Threshold	Second	Monitoring indicators and comparison Lucas/national monitoring	Second part

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

Biological topic	The analysis of the different indicators according to land use	colleagues' experience	Soil indicators
Insight on how to use the current EU projects monitoring work for the practical implementation of the coming SML	Biodiversity Sampling strategy	Parameters that are important to quantify soil health	Biological

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

All	Biological	Bio-indicators
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PREPSOIL – 2022-2025

Future proposals and needs: What topics, approaches, or additional skills would you like to see included in future training sessions?

-	/	Mapping, evaluation and sequestration	Indicators on monitoring
Soil nematodes	Mediterranean region particularities	How to read different analytical results in order to give advice about soil health	Data acces

Funded by Horizon Europe

Future proposals and needs: What topics, approaches, or additional skills would you like to see included in future training sessions?

How to interact with private initiatives	Thematic session by sectors: agriculture, forest, ...	the use of modelling in soil health	How to educate the public about these topics
Communication strategies	Practical examples how it is supposed to implement the smi in different countries.	Thresholds of the indicators	Standardized methods

Funded by Horizon Europe

Future proposals and needs: What topics, approaches, or additional skills would you like to see included in future training sessions?

More detailed session on indicators thresholds in different contexts	Integration of soil health indicators	Interpretation of the indicators values	Funding instruments availables
How to design a soil sampling strategy	It could be interesting to unclude all land uses into soil monitoring problematics	How fo find out what parameters are most important for distinct regions. Eg. Alpine or agricultural or forest soils. All soils matter.	How tl address the connexion between national systems and Lucas

Funded by Horizon Europe

Future proposals and needs: What topics, approaches, or additional skills would you like to see included in future training sessions?

Not only aspects of soil monitoring law but monitoring techniques that can be applied to farmers to follow changes in soil status parameters, and sampling strategies.	The thresholds of indicators established for each region and land use	Indicators value comparison between countries with similar edaphoclimatic conditions	Specific practical training for competent authorities on the SML provisions
Biogeographical differences	Theshold	Indicators values comparison between similar edaphoclimatic conditions	Soil health indexes

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What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

Future proposals and needs: What topics, approaches, or additional skills would you like to see included in future training sessions?

Overall assessment: What did you think of the session as a whole?

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Country of origin

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Country of origin

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What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

RS and Soil The two presentations about DSM All of them

remote sensing about digital soil mapping the conclusions DSM

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What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

Best Practices example from ES Remote sensing First talk: The methods for selecting the farms- Second talk: Broad and in depth overview of RS available for DSM and soil monitoring Interesting: The comparison between conventional and remote sensing of soil organic carbon. Useful information on remote sensing platforms.

Remote sensing provides direct access to certain soil information or makes soil property covariates available, with potentially very high spatial resolution.

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Future proposals and needs: What topics, approaches, or additional skills would you like to see included in future training sessions?

/ How can remote sensing data be used for soil health How to homogenize between the different national initiatives and be sure we can use digital soil mapping from a country to another without struggling in the comparison hands on how to get remote sensing data and how to work with it

How to integrate already existing monitoring schemes in the new EU scheme, so as to make use of this valuable data resource Machine Learning in Soil Definition of the thresholds for soil health descriptors Those related to regional/national policies related to Soil Health

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Future proposals and needs: What topics, approaches, or additional skills would you like to see included in future training sessions?

More about soil mapping Examples of how countries are implementing (or planning to implement) the SM law, and what must be done in detail what do farmers gain from soil monitoring? Soil database

what do farmers need to use soil health data in the field? Soil sampling procedures AI for monitoring soil Harmonization of procedures or development of tools to pass from certain estimates to other estimates of the same properties

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What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

All the content	Advantages and disadvantages of sampling techniques	The focus on the benefit for the farmers!	MRV and modeling approaches
Remote sensing	both presentations were well done because of clear visuals and speech	Lecture 2	Lecture 2

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

Modeling approaches to MRV	The different (and complementary) points of view for the different projects	Modeling	Defining baseline SOC
Lecture 3	Sampling design	Lecture 3	Soil Monitoring Strategies for Carbon Farming in Southern Europe

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

Lecture 4	Modelling	Sampling design and COS operational in Spain	Protocol for Monitoring Soil Carbon Stocks in Mediterranean Farms
Protocol for Monitoring Soil Carbon Stocks in Mediterranean Farms	Soil monitoring strategy	Mercedes presentation	Sampling efficiency, SOC monitoring alongside influencing factors on carbon storage, types of sampling i.e. systematic, stratified, and the links.

What part or content of the session did you find most useful or interesting?

the last one	SOC sampling	Teledetection	Soil biodiversity
All of them	Allowing Farmers contribution		

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Annex 3. Reference and supporting documents (training needs report, draft SML proposal)

Annex 3.1. Potential training needs for the implementation and transposition of the “Soil Monitoring Law”

PREPSOIL WP5 - T.5.4. Capacity building for improved monitoring knowledge base

INTERNAL IDENTIFICATION OF POTENTIAL TRAINING TOPICS

Potential training needs for the implementation and transposition of the “Soil Monitoring Law”

Reference docs:

[Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience \(Soil Monitoring Law\)](#) (5 July 2023)

[General approach from the Council of the European Union](#) (17 June 2024)

1. LEGAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

Proposed Content:

- **Details of the Directive and its relationship with other EU environmental regulations:** This includes understanding how the directive integrates with other environmental regulations and the broader EU regulatory framework.
- **Legal procedures for transposing the Directive into national legislation:** Guidance on how to adapt the provisions of the directive to national laws, including examples of best practices.
- **Rights and obligations of Member States:** Focus on the establishment of soil districts and the designation of competent authorities and "soil units."

Comments:

- **EC:** It is important to assess whether these topics are really necessary for Member States. A needs assessment can determine their relevance and adjust the content accordingly.

2. TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE OF SOIL AND ITS DESCRIPTORS

Proposed content:

- **Physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of soil:** Training in identifying and understanding key soil properties that affect its health and functionality.
- **Soil sampling and analysis methods:** Techniques for collecting representative samples and their laboratory analysis.
- **Interpretation of soil descriptors and soil health criteria:** Training in the use of indicators and thresholds to assess soil health.

Comments:

- **EC:** It is essential first to know how soil health indicators are estimated and then to be able to interpret these values with relevant reference data and thresholds.
- **PREPSOIL WP5:** Significant changes have occurred in biodiversity characterization in recent proposals. It is crucial to include harmonized sampling and analysis methods and consider the latest EU updates.

3. SOIL MONITORING AND EVALUATION

Proposed content:

- **Design and establishment of a soil monitoring framework:** Development of strategies for continuous and systematic soil monitoring.

This point is in line with point 1 of Article 23a of the Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law), which requires establishing a monitoring framework in accordance with Article 6 and determining sampling points as per Article 8(1) and (1a) and Part A.1 of Annex II.

- **Remote sensing techniques and use of spatial data:** Use of advanced technologies to collect data on soil status.
- **Soil health assessment and report preparation:** Methods to evaluate the collected information and present clear and accessible reports.

Comments:

- **EC:** Support in designing the sample survey and implementing quality management systems for laboratories is crucial.
- **PREPSOIL WP5:** Use examples of national monitoring systems in operation and consider PREPSOIL Deliverable T.4.2. The curriculum introduction should explain the concepts of soil health and quality.

4. SUSTAINABLE SOIL MANAGEMENT

Proposed content:

- **Principles and practices of sustainable soil management:** Focus on agricultural and forestry management techniques that preserve soil health.
- **Identification and mitigation of harmful management practices:** Training to identify and correct practices that harm the soil.
- **Implementation of soil regeneration practices:** Strategies for recovering degraded soils.

This point can benefit from the support indicated in Article 23a, points 2 and 6 of the Soil Monitoring Law, which establishes sustainable objective values and evaluates the critical loss of ecosystem services.

Comments:

- **PREPSOIL WP5:** It is vital to distinguish between agricultural fields and forest plots, and between types of soil degradation such as mineral and organic contamination.

5. MANAGEMENT OF CONTAMINATED SOILS

Proposed content:

- **Identification and assessment of potentially contaminated soils:** Methods to detect and assess soil contamination.

This point aligns with Article 23a, points 3 and 7 of the Soil Monitoring Law, which requires determining the list of organic pollutants and establishing a list of potentially contaminating activities.

- **Methodologies for investigating and managing soil contamination:** Procedures for treating and managing contaminated soils.
- **Development of action plans for the remediation of contaminated soils:** Creation of strategies for the recovery of soils affected by contaminants. This point also aligns with Article 23a, point 8.

Comments:

- **EC:** Consider integrating activities from existing projects like ARAGORN and ISLANDR.
- **PREPSOIL WP5:** A clear distinction must be made between types of soil contamination and degradation.

6. DIGITAL TOOLS AND DATA PORTAL

Proposed content:

- **Use of the digital data portal on soil health:** Training in accessing and using digital platforms for soil data management.
- **Integration of georeferenced data and its use in soil monitoring:** Use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for managing and analyzing spatial data.
- **Access and use of spatial databases:** Skills to access and use large spatial databases.

These points are supported by Article 23a, point 4 of the Soil Monitoring Law, which establishes the determination of values for soil sealing and soil destruction indicators.

Comments:

- **PREPSOIL WP5:** Clarify the differences between the subsections and ensure the protection of personal data in soil observations.

7. PUBLIC PARTICIPATION AND COMMUNICATION

Proposed content:

- **Effective communication strategies with the interested public:** Development of skills to communicate complex information in an accessible manner.
- **Transparency and access to environmental information:** Ensuring that information on soil health is transparent and accessible.
- **Procedures for public participation in decision-making:** Engaging the community and stakeholders in the decision-making process on soil management.

This point can be strengthened by Article 23a, point 5 of the Soil Monitoring Law, which establishes the determination or estimation of soil descriptors' values.

Comments:

- **EC:** Guidelines for training soil managers, landowners, and relevant authorities are essential.
- **PREPSOIL WP5:** Public participation is crucial for accessing information and contributing to data acquisition.

8. EVALUATION AND MONITORING OF IMPLEMENTATION

Proposed content:

- **Monitoring and evaluation techniques for the implementation of the Directive:** Methods to evaluate compliance and effectiveness of the directive.

This point aligns with Article 23a, point 1 of the Soil Monitoring Law, which requires establishing a monitoring framework.

- **Performance indicators and trend evaluation:** Use of indicators to measure progress and long-term trends.
- **Reporting and documenting progress:** Training in writing reports and documenting advances in implementation.

Annex 3.2. Report on training needs for pilot courses on soil health indicators and the existing policy framework

PREPSOIL WP5 - T.5.4. Capacity building for improved monitoring knowledge base

DRAFT PROGRAMME FOR PILOT TRAININGS ON SOIL HEALTH INDICATORS AND THE CURRENT REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

GENERAL OBJECTIVE OF THE PROGRAM

The main objective of the program is to train public officials who manage or will manage soil health data under a unified reporting system, policymakers who make decisions based on these indicators, and members of Living Labs who drive innovation and co-creation of solutions, by providing a comprehensive understanding of soil health indicators and their application within a continuously evolving regulatory and technical framework.

Participants will aim to:

- Develop an in-depth knowledge of soil functions and their role in environmental, food, and climate sustainability.
- Understand the complexity and challenges associated with defining, measuring, and applying indicators, particularly in diverse contexts such as geographic regions and specific land uses.
- Critically analyze the advances and limitations of the **Soil Monitoring Law (SML)** and the **Mission Soil initiatives**, promoting flexible and adaptive approaches that address local needs while maintaining harmonized European-level objectives.
- Acquire practical tools to implement monitoring strategies and formulate public policies based on scientific evidence and robust data.

This program combines theoretical and practical training to empower policymakers to make informed decisions, considering both the opportunities and challenges faced by soil management in Europe and globally.

DETAILED PROGRAMME

MODULE 1: FOUNDATIONS AND GLOBAL CONTEXT

[Presentation 1: Soil Health in the 21st Century](#)

Objective: Establish a conceptual framework on the importance of soil and the global challenges associated with its management.

Contents:

- **Functions and ecosystem services of soil:** Ecosystem services according to FAO: supply of food, fibers, and fuels. Habitat for organisms. Flood regulation. Source of pharmaceuticals and genetic resources. Basis for human infrastructure. Supply of construction materials. Cultural heritage. Carbon retention. Water purification and reduction of soil contaminants. Climate regulation. Nutrient cycling.
- **Main global threats:** Erosion, compaction, acidification, contamination, sealing, salinization, waterlogging, nutrient imbalance (deficiency or excess), and loss of organic carbon and biodiversity.
- **Emerging challenges:** climate change, emerging pollutants (e.g., PFAS, microplastics).
- **Global perspective:** United Nations initiatives: Sustainable Development Goals, FAO, and IPCC.
- **European perspective:** EU initiatives, including the Soil Monitoring Law (SML), Mission Soil. "Farm to Fork" Strategy, EU Soil Strategy for 2030, Biodiversity Strategy, Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture, and Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation.
 - **SML:**
 - Main objectives, structure, and proposal of key indicators.
 - Concerns raised by Member States: Harmonization vs. local flexibility. Integration of the directive with existing national initiatives. Sampling strategies. The use of a single threshold to define healthy/unhealthy soils. Definition of different health levels.
 - **Mission Soil:**
 - Living Labs and Lighthouses as experimental and demonstrative environments.
 - Applied technological tools: Remote sensing, GIS, digital platforms.
 - Normative and technical impact: Connection between SML, Mission Soil, and local needs.

Group Debate: What local challenges do soils face in your regions? Example: Soil artificialization.

MODULE 2: KEY INDICATORS AND THEIR COMPLEXITY

[Presentation 2: Key Indicators and Their Complexity](#)

Objective: Understand the scientific and technical basis behind soil health indicators and the challenges in their application.

Contents:

- **Physical indicators:** Bulk density, structural stability, water retention capacity, erosion rate, porosity, depth of topsoil horizon, infiltration and runoff, penetration resistance, among others.
- **Chemical indicators:** Soil Organic Carbon (SOC), salinity, pH, contamination, nutrients, cation exchange capacity, exchangeable cations, and others.

- **Biological indicators:** Microbial biodiversity, basal respiration, enzymatic activity.
- **Detailed study of the indicators proposed in the SML:**
 - SOC, biodiversity, bulk density, sealing, erosion, salinity and contamination, nutrient excess, subsoil compaction, reduction of soil water retention capacity, acidification, arable layer compaction, soil biodiversity loss, land occupation, and sealing.
 - Analysis of their relevance and applicability in different contexts and types of land use. Uncertainty/precision of the indicators.
 - Evaluation of how harmonized thresholds may influence national and regional policies.
- **The need for flexible approaches that consider regional particularities and land uses.** Emphasizing a holistic vision to address problems (avoiding the unintended exacerbation of other issues while trying to control a specific one). For example, carbon content can be increased by adding more nitrogen, but this may lead to eutrophication or GHG emissions.
- **Directed questions:** Which indicators are most relevant in specific contexts?

MODULE 3: MONITORING METHODS AND ADVANCED TECHNOLOGIES

Presentation 3: Monitoring Methods

Objective: Explain how to conduct soil health indicator monitoring, from planning to implementation, ensuring representativeness and accuracy.

Contents:

- **Basic principles for indicator monitoring:**
 - Clear objective definition according to local and regional contexts.
 - Identification of key indicators to monitor (SOC, biodiversity, salinity, among others). **It may be necessary to distinguish between indicators that are relevant to measure in all soils (e.g., SOC, structural stability, biodiversity, etc.) and indicators that are only relevant to measure in certain contexts (salinity, certain types of contamination, etc.).**
- **Designing representative monitoring plans:**
 - Selection of sampling points based on degradation risks and spatial representativeness.
 - Monitoring frequency to ensure updated data.
- **Practical methods for data collection:**
 - Manual and traditional procedures adapted to different contexts.
 - Integration of adaptive approaches based on soil type (agricultural, forest, urban, mixed).
- **Preparation of a basic monitoring plan adapted to a case study.**

Presentation 4: Digital Technologies for Monitoring and Data Analysis

Objective: Provide participants with information on digital and technological tools needed to monitor and analyze soil health indicators accurately and efficiently.

Contents:

- **Using the digital soil health data portal:**
 - Training on access and use of digital platforms for soil data management.
- **Integration of georeferenced data and its use in indicator monitoring:**
 - Use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to manage and analyze spatial data.
- **Advanced technologies as support:**
 - Remote sensing for capturing high-resolution data and integrating it into digital platforms.
 - In-situ sensors connected to digital systems for continuous monitoring of chemical and biological indicators.
- **Accessing and using large spatial databases:**
 - Developing skills to access, analyze, and utilize spatial databases in the context of soil monitoring.
- **Relation to Article 23a, Point 4 of the SML:** Determination of values for indicators such as sealing and soil destruction through digital integration.

MODULE 4: INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS AND DECISION-MAKING

Presentation 5: Indicator Evaluation and Report Preparation

Objective: Train participants in the critical interpretation of data and effective communication of results. Explore how to integrate results into the formulation of effective public policies.

Contents:

- **Evaluation of scenarios and analysis of the impact of different land management strategies** (agricultural practices, forestry, etc.), with application of models for evidence-based decision-making.
- **Comparative interpretation:** Normative thresholds and local adaptations.
- **Success examples in the implementation of soil policies based on data.**